

Combating heat stress through urban planning: integrated case studies for Lisbon and Islamabad

Abstract: Nature-based solutions are often proposed as adaptation techniques to heat stress and high temperatures in cities all over the world, but quantifications of their potential effectiveness are lacking. In Lisbon and Islamabad we co-designed, together with local stakeholders, a selection of urban planning strategies using commonly proposed green and blue infrastructure solutions from literature. Their effectiveness in reducing temperature and heat stress on climatological time scales were simulated using the UrbClim model, allowing spatial resolutions up to the meter-scale, while potential benefits for sleep loss, heat stress and heatwave exposure were quantified using CLIMADA. Green and blue infrastructure generally offer local relief with respect to heat stress, reducing heat stress days by up to 40 %, mainly by providing shading from direct sunlight and by reducing land surface temperatures. Nighttime temperatures are most efficiently reduced by unsealing urban areas, while daytime temperatures benefit most from increases in high vegetation and trees (both up to 0.5 °C). To maximize benefits for the population, urban planning strategies should focus on areas with highest population densities, as temperature reductions and heat stress relief quickly decay outside of the areas of intervention. Despite their proven positive effects, the investigated green and blue urban planning strategies clearly reveal limits to adaptation towards the future, especially in a Current Policies scenario, as they only offset part of the projected heat stress impacts.

1. Introduction

Heat is considered one of the most impactful natural climate disasters at present time, with approximately 500.000 fatalities each year (Zhao et al., 2021). With climate change causing an increase in the frequency and intensity of extreme temperatures, populations are expected to experience a sharp increase in heat exposure (Li et al., 2020). Apart from physical health-related risks, excessive heat has several other impacts, such as decreased productivity of workers & GDP (Orlov et al., 2020; M. Zhao et al., 2021; Kotz et al., 2024), increased energy consumption (Santamouris et al., 2015), crime rates (Chersich et al., 2019) and numbers of depression and mental health problems (Thompson et al., 2023). Populations in cities are especially vulnerable (Brown, 2020) since additional effects such as the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect (Oke, 1982) contribute to even higher temperatures. Furthermore, heatwave exposure in cities is expected to increase even faster with climate change and future

urbanization (Fischer et al., 2012; Wouters et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2022). Outdoor heat stress also persists indoors (Ma et al., 2023), limiting a person's cooling potential (Jiang et al., 2023). Poor communities and vulnerable populations are most affected, as their dwellings often lack proper insulation, A/C and other cooling facilities (Souverijns et al., 2022).

To minimize heat stress exposure in cities towards the future, global warming should be restricted to levels as low as possible and preferably within the limits of the Paris Agreement (global average temperatures well below 2 °C compared to pre-industrial levels). However, some warming and risks will be unavoidable. As such, adaptation and increased preparedness to extreme heat are options that need to be considered to create resilience for city populations (Hatvani-Kovacs et al., 2016).

Smart urban planning offers tools to reduce temperatures and heat stress in cities. In this respect, several design options can be considered. Nature-based solutions (NBS) and more specific green and blue infrastructure (GBI) usually form the basis of measures to reduce temperatures in cities. A recent review by Kumar et al. (2024) showed its potential of daytime temperature reduction of several degrees over cities all over the world. By modifying existing infrastructure, also reductions in heat stress have been observed in different studies (Kabisch et al., 2016; Augusto et al., 2020). Schwaab et al., (2021) observed that urban trees reduced surface temperatures up to 12 °C over 293 European cities, while air temperatures in Beijing old city could drop by more than 1 °C by applying several NBS strategies (Su et al., 2022). In a study in England, woodland outperformed blue infrastructure in cooling efficiency (Sahani et al., 2023). Singapore is probably the city with the longest-term vision on green adaptation, with the first projects and tree planting already starting in 1960. This evolved in the following decades to transform the city towards a 'City in Nature' (Cui et al., 2021) and increased the resilience of the city not only for flood control, but also for coastal protection and heat adaptation (Chow, 2018).

Apart from direct reductions of heat, downstream benefits on public health (Kabisch et al., 2017; van den Bosch & Ode Sang, 2017), biodiversity (Epelde et al., 2022) and other socio-economic sectors (Panno et al., 2017; Vervoort et al., 2024) have also been identified. Furthermore, several studies have identified NBS to be cost-efficient (Van Zanten et al., 2023; Takacs et al., 2025) and to have large public support and acceptance from citizens (Badura et al., 2021).

Frantzeskaki (2019) showcases the importance of co-creating NBS with diverse stakeholders, local government agents and citizens. An integrated approach resulting from the engagement of different urban actors is required to ensure inclusivity, liveability and resilience. Stakeholder engagement therefore fosters solutions that are socially equitable and context-specific, enhancing the legitimacy and acceptance of adaptation measures (Mees et al., 2012, 2019). Furthermore, participatory approaches have been shown to improve the implementation and sustainability of adaptation initiatives by aligning them with local priorities and resources (Fisher et al., 2022). This underscores the necessity of inclusive, collaborative frameworks to address the complex challenges posed by urban climate change.

In order to assess heat stress and the effect of NBS and GBI on temperatures and heat stress in city environments, several tools are available. Satellite observations provide spatially detailed information, but have fixed-term overpass times, can be prohibited by clouds and their thermal bands are limited to measuring surface temperatures (Almeida et al., 2021). The latter is not always a good proxy for air temperatures, which is often needed for calculating downstream impacts. Furthermore, heat stress is often calculated as a combination of radiation, air temperature, wind speed and moisture, and summarized in indices as the Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT) or Universal Thermal Comfort Index (Budd, 2008; Blazejczyk et al., 2012). In order to take these factors into account, climate models might offer a solution. They provide consistent results in both time and space, allow to capture the requested atmospheric variables and offer the option to vary land use characteristics to account for (potential future) climate change adaptation. Significant limiting factors exist, for example their spatial resolution and the computational power required to obtain results. Weather Research and Forecasting Model (WRF) for example is able to perform high-resolution simulations over city environments, but requires several nesting steps at high computational costs (e.g. Mughal et al., 2020). Another option is to turn to more simple urban boundary layer models and microscale models, that allow to simulate meteorological and climatological information for limited areas (Lobaccaro et al., 2021).

Recent studies have identified that the efficacy of green infrastructure and NBS can differ substantially, even within cities (Makido et al., 2019; Cortinovis et al., 2022). More detailed analyses and replicable protocols are needed to provide urban decision-makers with the right information (Seddon et al., 2020; Probst et al., 2022; Ferrario et al., 2024).

In this paper, we contribute to the growing evidence of the efficacy of GBI in two different urban contexts, namely Lisbon (Portugal) and Islamabad (Pakistan). These cities were selected based on their specific and contrasting socio-economic vulnerabilities that overlay with the common physical heat stress risk that is present in both regions, while also providing the

perspective of developed and developing countries and differing urban planning approaches. Both regions also offered substantial stakeholder engagement opportunities, therefore providing a practical testbed for generalisable urban planning approaches. We aim to answer the following research questions:

- What is the effect of a set of co-designed GBI on temperature, heat stress and the resulting impacts on the population, and how do they differ from each other?
- How big is the impact mitigation potential of different GBIs with respect to (future) climate change?

2. Methodology

A summary of the methodological steps in this paper can be found in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Summary of the methodological workflow

2.1. Study areas

2.1.1. Lisbon Metropolitan Area

The Lisbon Metropolitan Area (LMA) is located in the south-centre coastal area of Portugal and includes 18 municipalities with approximately three million inhabitants. The LMA

population corresponds to 27% of the total resident population in Portugal, 26% of employment and 48% of national business production.

A wide range of climate-related hazards exist for the LMA. Extreme temperatures and compounding events such as droughts, water scarcity, forest fires and related agricultural yield and species losses are identified as key climate risks in the region (Guiot & Cramer, 2016). The high concentration of population in the LMA showcases a potentially significant increase in exposure to these climate risks towards the future. Apart from the permanently residing population, the tourism sector, an important economic sector in the region, is also heavily affected by climate risks, as increasing temperatures affect thermal comfort, which plays an increasing role in the attractiveness of a destination (Lopes et al., 2022).

Adaptation to climate change is of high importance in the LMA. Apart from national climate adaptation plans in which heat stress is covered, also a Metropolitan Adaptation Strategic Plan for heatwaves for the LMA exists (Pina et al., 2019). Many of the 18 municipalities drafted their own strategies and plans for climate change adaptation. These include territorial plans under different future climate scenarios, focusing on different sectors that are of interest for the community, such as for example agriculture and tourism.

2.1.2. Islamabad

The city of Islamabad lies at the foothills of Margalla, an extension of the Himalayas, and houses approximately two million people. Islamabad did not evolve like other naturally developing cities of the country, but was a planned city designed in 1960 to replace the first capital Karachi, which was turning into a congested urban area with limited space for further expansion and increasingly higher living costs. Islamabad has faced significant urban growth and expansion in the past two and a half decades and has evolved into the 9th largest city of the country in terms of population.

Climate risks in the region are related to floods, droughts, water scarcity as well as heatwaves and affect public health, water management, energy production and labour productivity in the region. Current heat stress adaptation interventions in Islamabad mainly include seasonal preparations where emergency heat stress wards are set up in hospitals, school timings shift to cooler morning hours or online, and preventive guidelines dissemination via media. However, long term heat responsive urban planning is still in nascent phases, lagging far behind the rapid ongoing development of heat hotspots and encroachment of natural green-blue corridors. Among implemented city planning adaptation measures, the development of Miyawaki Urban Forests has gained precedence in the recent past (Miyawaki, 1998). As a

means to revive green elements within dense city infrastructure, reduce UHI impact, and improve air quality, tree plantation has experienced a boom especially since the landmark country wide afforestation project, the Ten Billion Tree Tsunami (Arshad et al., 2022).

2.2. Adaptation design

To design adaptation plans for heat mitigation for the purpose of this study, the spatial capacity of the study areas to regulate heat, focusing on the composition and configuration of green and blue spaces, or areas with potential for such transformations, were evaluated. The analysis emphasizes the role of ecological structures, non-built-up spaces, and areas along infrastructural networks in mitigating heat stress and supporting climate adaptation.

Five key dimensions were considered to be crucial for the proposed adaptation measures to gauge their effectiveness and that should be considered in their design:

1. Coherence with physical and ecological conditions by aligning with topography and ecologically valuable areas (that can provide cooling services) (Kuzniecowa Bacchin, 2015).
2. Connectivity through hydrographic and mobility axes as potential networks for regional ventilation and cooling (Hermy et al., 2005).
3. Everyday movement patterns of the population and the transformation of spaces near amenities and daily transit routes into cooling areas (Vigano et al., 2016).
4. Influence of land-use/land-cover types, governance structures, and ownership patterns that influence spatial adjustments.
5. Alignment of proposed cooling strategies with existing protection and conservation frameworks (Pina et al., 2019).

Stakeholder engagement was instrumental in the development process of adaptation planning design, providing crucial insights into key hazards faced by cities' vulnerable hotspots and offering valuable local knowledge for designing adaptation options.

The stakeholder engagement process began in August 2021 and continued over the next 3 years, until final engagement meetings in November and December 2024 (Davidel et al., 2024). The stakeholders' pool was kept diverse including representatives from the climate change governance sector, development partners, research and academia, and private sector. Webinars and workshops were organised to connect with the different stakeholders approximately every 6 months. Each of these meetings involved group discussions to create a strong and engaged stakeholder base and to gather information relevant for the LMA and Islamabad.

The stakeholder meetings resulted in the (i) evaluation of the proposed strategies/measures of adaptation to heat stress, which were ranked in reference to their efficiency; (ii) a selection of strategies and measures according to the existing land use and function, plans, regulations and policies of the LMA and the sectoral priorities of its municipalities, taking into account the five dimensions listed above; (iii) the final hierarchical classification based on insights of their performance effectiveness in the face of different future climate scenarios (e.g. tree-lined roads are most efficient in future climate change scenarios in streets that are facing along the N-S axis in the LMA).

By selecting known areas within their regions and including their recommendations and local expert knowledge in the designs, the stakeholders felt more connected to the project, which also resulted in reduced stakeholder fatigue. The inclusion of their recommendations also benefited the final designs that were applied, as their local expert knowledge was vital to obtain realistic and practically applicable adaptation scenarios. As an example, the initial urban development proposed in the E-11 sector were criticized by the local stakeholders, as they were not taking into account enough the local building style and practices. Their recommendations, matching local experiences with administrative/legal limitations, were adopted in the final design. As such, their involvement, together with the consideration of local regulation and urban design principles increased the probability of realistic adaptation designs. More details about the stakeholder engagement process and the different steps that led to the final designs can be retrieved from Davidel et al. (2024).

2.3. Heat stress and impact modeling

2.3.1. UrbClim modeling over the Lisbon Metropolitan Area

To simulate the effect of urban planning design on heat stress and other downstream impacts, different elements influencing heat stress need to be considered. Heat stress is often quantified by investigating temperatures, but in many regions, also moisture, radiation and wind speed are considered important variables explaining thermal comfort of humans (i.e. the heat index or the WBGT) (Lo et al., 2023).

To quantify this meteorological information at high spatial and temporal resolution, the UrbClim model is used (De Ridder et al., 2015). The UrbClim model is a 3D atmospheric boundary layer model with a detailed land surface scheme and simplified urban physics (De Ridder & Schayes, 1997). The UrbClim model provides meteorological information at speeds of two orders of magnitude faster compared to standard meso-scale models, while retaining similar accuracies (García-Díez et al., 2016; Lauwaet et al., 2024). This is especially useful in the

adaptation modeling framework proposed here, as it enables the execution of multiple long-term simulations with different urban planning designs.

The LMA spans an area of almost 100 x 100 km (Figure 2). As a baseline, the model is set up for present-day climate and land use conditions, and a simulation was executed at 300 m spatial resolution for the time period 2011-2020. The meteorological synoptic forcing for the UrbClim model is obtained from ERA-5 reanalysis data (Hersbach et al., 2020) providing 2D and 3D meteorological input information at 31 km spatial resolution. In order to accurately perform the dynamical downscaling to 300m, a detailed representation of the land surface is needed. Land use is defined from ESA WorldCover, providing global land use information at 10m spatial resolution (Zanaga et al., 2021). The urban land use class is further split into a dense urban and suburban class by including information from the Global Human Settlement Layer, containing building fraction information (Corbane et al., 2021). Other soil parameters such as soil sealing fraction and the fraction of vegetation are derived from LANDSAT or by combining information from different satellite constellations (Zhang et al., 2020). Information on the anthropogenic heat fluxes within the domain is obtained at 1 km spatial resolution (Jin et al., 2019), while terrain height is obtained from the Copernicus Digital Elevation Model at 30m resolution (ESA). A detailed description of the model setup can be found in Souverijns et al. (2026). The 300 m results were further downscaled statistically to 100 m using a moving window regression approach and integrating the high-resolution land cover and LANDSAT information as predictors.

UrbClim model	
Meteorological boundary input	ERA-5 (Hersbach et al., 2020)
Future climate change	MESMER-M (Nath et al., 2022)
Land use	ESA WorldCover (Zanaga et al., 2021)
Building fraction	Global Human Settlement Layer (Corbane et al., 2021)
Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	Landsat
Soil sealing fraction	Zhang et al. (2020)
Anthropogenic Heat Flux	Jin et al. (2019)
Digital Elevation Model	Copernicus DEM
Meter-scale modelling (HiREx)	
Building footprints	Open Street Map Microsoft Building Footprints
Building height and tree footprints	Copernicus Urban Atlas
CLIMADA	
Exposure information	Worldpop constrained UN-adjusted 2020 population distribution (Bondarenko et al., 2020)
Impact function (sleep loss)	Minor et al. (2022)

Table 1: Overview of the different input datasets used by the different model components

Figure 2: Domains of study with their current present-day land use. Satellite images are provided for reference for the case study areas.

The UrbClim model provides information at surface, soil and atmospheric levels, of which 2 m temperature, humidity, wind speed and land surface temperature are retained at hourly time scales. This information was used to calculate heat stress (WBGT) following the methodology of Liljegren et al. (2008). To calculate WBGT, apart from meteorological input, a detailed representation of radiation (obtained from ERA-5) and local shadows is needed. For the latter, the sky view factor is calculated using information on the building characteristics in the city. This information is obtained via OpenStreetMap & the Microsoft Building Footprint dataset and processed into a sky view factor at 100 m spatial resolution for the full LMA using the method of Dirksen et al. (2019). The UrbClim results over Lisbon were validated by comparing against several meteorological stations that fall within the LMA (https://destinationearth.marvin.vito.be/download/technical_report.pdf).

Apart from present land use and climate conditions, also simulations taking into account future climate and urban planning strategies at the regional level are executed. For future climate, several scenarios defined by the IPCC AR6 report have been calculated:

- Current Policies (CurPol in IPCC AR6): No further climate action beyond currently undertaken policies, with global warming going unabated and reaching approximately 2.9°C in 2100.
- Delayed Climate Action (IMP-GS in IPCC AR6): Decarbonisation is delayed until 2030, after which a rapid decline takes place. Carbon dioxide removal compensates for remaining fossil fuel emissions and global warming reaches 1.7°C in 2100.
- Shifting Pathways (IMP-SP in IPCC AR6): Sustainable development with stringent climate policies. Global warming peaks at 1.6°C in 2060 and goes back to 1.3°C by 2100.

The future meteorological information to drive the UrbClim model is obtained by combining simulations from the MESMER-M climate emulator (Nath et al., 2022), which translates global temperature changes obtained by the FalR emulator to local responses (Smith et al., 2018), with the higher temporal resolution obtained from the CMIP6 archive. This way, an ensemble considering stochastic and natural variability, differences in global mean temperature responses and local variability is created. The applied methodology is detailed in Schwaab et al. (2024) and Souverijns et al. (2026). The median, 5th and 95th percentile of the future climate ensemble projections is retained. Different adaptation designs are reflected into a change in the land use representation. For different combinations of (future) climate and land use (adaptation), UrbClim is re-executed to quantify the effect of different designs on temperature and heat stress.

2.3.2. Meter-scale modeling over Lisbon, Almada & Islamabad

Apart from heat stress assessments at the regional level at 100 m resolution, more detailed case studies were executed for limited areas at the meter-scale level. This aids to identify heat stress at the level of streets and buildings and to quantify the effect of small-scale localized adaptation measures. For this, the HiREx model can be used (Souverijns et al., 2023). At such detailed spatial resolutions, it is important to accurately represent individual features in the city, such as individual trees, buildings (including their height), streets and other land cover types. This work was executed for two case study areas of 500 m x 500 m in the LMA (Lisbon and Almada municipalities) and one area of 2 x 2 km in Islamabad (the E-11 sector; Figure 2).

For the Lisbon and Almada case studies, data from different sources was gathered. Open Street Map provided detailed information on building locations, street geometries, water bodies and even some individual trees were identified. This database was complemented with land use, building height and tree location information from the Copernicus Urban Atlas. Some missing building footprints were obtained from the Microsoft Building Footprint dataset. A visual comparison with satellite imagery of both domains was executed to validate the obtained land use map of the region. Manual modifications were executed to complement missing features.

For the E-11 sector in Islamabad, detailed open-source land use information was lacking. Therefore, a local land use map was obtained via an external mapping company containing information on roads, trees, water bodies and buildings, together with a high-resolution Digital Surface Model, from which the height of the different individual features could be extracted.

Combining this detailed land use representation with meteorological input data obtained from the UrbClim model, WBGT at 1 m spatial resolution was calculated. The HiREx module was run for single representative heatwave days that recently occurred (16/07/2020 for the Lisbon and Almada case studies and 10/07/2020 for the E-11 case study), and their equivalent for different periods (mid- and end-century) in the 21st-century climate for each of the future climate scenarios.

2.4. CLIMADA impact model

Going beyond the description of the climate hazard, we also modeled the population affected by temperatures and heat stress, using the open-source risk modelling platform CLIMADA for the LMA (Aznar-Siguan & Bresch, 2019). This provides a more nuanced picture on the benefits of adaptation options. CLIMADA is based on the IPCC concept of risk and combines hazard (a map of event intensities), exposure (a map of individuals that are exposed to a hazard), and vulnerability (impact functions that determine the degree of effect from a certain hazard on the individuals constituting the exposure) to calculate risk. From a given hazard, exposure, and vulnerability an impact can be calculated. Here we use the 100 m resolution UrbClim information as hazard information and the 100 m resolution Worldpop constrained UN-adjusted 2020 population distribution map (Bondarenko et al., 2020) as exposure. In this study, we focus on how risk changes due to the evolution of its hazard component. We also do not differentiate vulnerabilities of different populations and only count the total number of people affected. Also, no changes in the population distribution towards the future are included. This simplification originates from the lack of future projections of population

(distribution) at the scale of the analysis (sub-city scale). A detailed vulnerability assessment derived from a set of interviews is presented in a separate study (McCaughey et al., in review).

The following impacts are calculated:

- The population exposed to extreme heat stress days (defined as the number of days in which the WBGT exceeds 31°C)
- The population exposed to heatwave days (defined as at least 6 consecutive days with a maximum temperature of 5 °C above the mean daily maximum temperature over 2011 - 2020)
- The average minutes of sleep loss (the impact function mapping the daily minimum temperature to the minutes of sleep loss is based on research showing that people tended to experience reduced sleeping duration under a warming climate; Minor et al., 2022).

The population exposed to extreme heat stress days per year and the population exposed to heatwave days per year are expressed as the hazard X person. Thus, the value of impact of 10 can represent both 1 person exposed to 10 hazards or 10 persons exposed to 1 hazard. The average minutes of sleep loss is expressed as the minutes of sleep loss obtained by the impact function X person. Thus, the value of impact of 10 can represent both 1 person losing 10 minutes or 10 persons losing 1 minute of sleep per year. We then compute the impact per year from 2020-2100 following the three climate change scenarios defined in Section 2.3.1, and for each of these, with and without every single adaptation option. The final results are expressed respectively as the average number of extreme heat stress person days, the average number of heatwave person days and person minutes of sleep loss per year in each decade. In order to signify the impacts on households, grids with less than 5 people were not included.

3. Results

3.1. Adaptation designs

3.1.1. Lisbon Metropolitan Area

Based on the adaptation design methodology and the five key dimensions described in Section 2.2, a catalogue of spatial capacity maps and heat stress reduction measures were created for the LMA (Annex 1 in Davidel et al., 2024). The adaptation strategies were tailored with varying intensities of action in collaboration with the stakeholders. As a result, three

adaptation policy recommendations were selected, leading to five different scenarios (Figure 3):

- **Soil unsealing** of urbanized and infrastructural areas, through an average increase of 20% of the non-paved area of urban and mobility infrastructure surfaces, and their replacement with low vegetation.
- Strategic increase in high vegetation (woodland) in:
 - All nationally designated **ecological corridors** (areas for the protection of ecological value, species migration and conservation of riparian zones; (Matos, 2018)) by wooded cover. Existing vegetation is substituted with woody plants, to evaluate the potential of the ecological corridors to act as cooling infrastructure for the LMA.
 - **Infrastructural verges** within a buffer of 822 m and 117 m around motorways and primary roads (following the delineation of zones of research on the effects on vegetation around road infrastructure, with their sizes varying according to their rank, as proposed by Vigano et al., 2016), to investigate the utilization of the transport axes that permeate both the urban areas and the whole metropolitan area as ventilation infrastructure.
 - Any additional and accessible open spaces in close proximity to the same mobility infrastructure axes, to provide both a regional system of urban forests and **parks** in peri-urban and extra-urban areas to act as cool spots, as well as to strengthen the system of a green-grid further than merely linear green elements and towards linear interconnected green patches and, thus, increase air ventilation.
- Increase in the tree cover of areas of agricultural production that lie on flat terrain via the promotion of **agroforestry** regimes (Pina et al., 2019), especially in cases where crops are exposed to higher temperatures due to local geomorphology.

Figure 3: Individual spatial strategies and measures composing the overall adaptation narrative of the Lisbon Metropolitan Area against higher temperatures, heat stress and associated extremes.

3.1.2. Lisbon case study

The Lisbon case study is located in a low-density urban area. Former social housing projects are the predominantly urban feature in the area, with additional services, education and sporting elements, and with a very pronounced mobility axis (railway) dividing the area from north to south. The adaptation strategy developed attains a more structural character, consisting of an (almost) contiguous structure of peri-urban forest/park framing that envelops the current and future urban developments. In specific, the strategy includes (Figure 4):

- **Greening** as a structural function, by allocating high vegetation (trees) in wider spaces spanning existing and planned corridors, such as roads and railways, going north-south and west-east, essentially, enveloping the current and future urban developments.
- **Infusing the urban tissue** (both current and planned) with individual trees, cool spots and unsealed surfaces on paved areas currently dedicated to cars, urban squares or internal urban block/building courtyards.
- **Tactically designed cooler spots** using broadleaf trees wherever possible.

3.1.3. Almada case study

The Almada case study is located in a dense, historical urban area of the city where housing, services, education and extremely high levels of mobility are important features. The adaptation strategy developed for this case study consists of a generalized soil unsealing strategy with a tactical implementation of cool spaces whenever possible, while individual trees complete the picture. In specific, the strategy includes (Figure 4):

- **Unsealing** paved surfaces currently utilized as car parks or squares, using permeable materials with low vegetation, complemented with the use of individual broadleaf trees when possible/feasible.
- **Greening** as a pragmatic strategy - rather than structural due to the specificity of the built environment - by increasing both high (trees) and low (grassland) vegetation, where it seems feasible to be done, while ensuring connectivity whenever possible.
- **Cooling** spots promotion (populated by high vegetation) in public (urban forests/parks), semi-private (internal block courtyards) and private areas (private

gardens). In the hotspot area, these are bound together by two axes (west-east & north-south) using additional individual tree planting.

3.1.4. E-11 case study

In the E-11 sector of Islamabad, apart from adaptation measures related to heat stress discussed above, we also considered mitigation measures that would make the green-blue network more resilient to future flooding events, based on stakeholder recommendations. For this purpose, new infiltration zones were created, natural streams, which were diverted into narrow conduits, were reopened, and the demolition of properties that were encroaching in the drainage system has been proposed. The adaptation scenario narrative high-resolution map that synthesises the existing and proposed spatial structures focuses mainly on four applied measures (Figure 4):

- The development of **green-blue corridors and green riparian zones**
- The development of a system of **urban forests and parks**
- The establishment of **green avenues and tree-lined streets**
- Proposals for climate resilient **urban developments**

Figure 4: Original (left) and adaptation (right) land use for the three case studies. Lisbon and Almada in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area and the E-11 sector in Islamabad.

3.2. Adaptation potential for heat stress

The GBI strategies proposed above include a set of large-scale infrastructural changes that come with significant socio-economic investments. In order to validate their effect and potential benefits on reducing heat stress and related impacts, it is important to provide a solid quantification of their potential benefits.

3.2.1. Lisbon Metropolitan Area

For each of the different adaptation scenarios proposed for the LMA, the impact on average yearly minimum and maximum temperature and the number of heat stress days (defined as the number of days in which WBGT exceeds 25°C) is calculated (Figure 5). Present-day (2011-2020) absolute values for these indicators over the LMA are presented in the appendix (Figure S1).

Different adaptation measures have varying effects on different climatological parameters. Unsealing the city impacts mainly night-time temperatures and is efficient in lowering the UHI effect by up to 0.5 °C in the densest building areas, even though only an unsealing fraction of 20 % is applied (Figure 5). Less heat is stored during the day when unsealing surfaces, leading to lower heat release during the night. The nighttime cooling effect of unsealing also propagates towards neighboring pixels, showing also temperature benefits outside the urban fabric. Unsealing the surface also has an effect on the amount of heat stress days, as reductions in the order of 10-20 % are obtained. This can be related to lower land surface temperatures of unsealed areas and related lower amounts of radiation that are emitted by these surfaces to people walking in the city (Eingrüber et al., 2024). The effect on maximum temperatures is however limited (even a small increase in temperatures is observed). This can be related to a lowering of the albedo when replacing sealed surfaces by low vegetation (Akbari et al., 2009) and the limited general influence of the urban fabric on daytime air temperatures in the LMA. Large-scale meteorology, topography and distance to the coast seem to be the most important drivers for daytime temperatures (Figure S1).

Tree planting is an effective measure to decrease maximum temperatures. Single trees can lower temperatures during the hottest hours of the day by several tenths of degrees, but large patches of trees offer benefits that can go up to 0.5°C (Figure 5). With respect to heat stress, reductions of up to 50% are achieved, a substantial improvement compared to current climatological conditions. Larger tree patches provide more efficient heat stress reduction and

daytime cooling effects compared to single trees or smaller patches. One notable effect of massive tree planting is that they could potentially increase night-time temperatures by more than 0.5°C. Trees in our designs generally have a high percentage of aggregation, which allows for the positive benefits of shade, evaporative cooling and reductions of air temperatures and heat stress during the day. During the night however, the high level of aggregation limits radiative cooling of the surface as heat is trapped between the surface and the canopy of the trees. This effect is the largest at the end of the night, during which open surfaces benefited most from radiative cooling, explaining the increase in nighttime temperatures caused by trees. In our simulations, we limited tree planting to the locations that were currently open spaces in the LMA, favoring this outcome. It should therefore be considered when implementing dense and close canopies in current open areas that, although a significant positive effect on daytime heat stress and temperatures, it may decrease radiative cooling during the night and increase nighttime temperatures. This effect was also observed experimentally by Beele et al. (2024).

The efficiency of the adaptation measures in future climates remain similar, with a slight decrease in the potential of greening with respect to the decrease in heat stress days in the Current Policies scenario by the end of the century (Figure S2).

Figure 5: The effect of different urban planning scenarios (rows) on different yearly average climate parameters (columns) in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area in a present-day climate (2011-2020). For temperatures, absolute differences are shown, for heat stress days, the differences are visualized on a relative scale. Thin black lines denote coastlines.

To calculate impacts of changes in temperature and heat stress, the exposure of population on the different climate parameters discussed above is calculated. Under the Current Policies scenario, the LMA experiences a rapid increase in the sum of the population exposed to extreme heat stress days, rising by up to a mean of 600% by the end of the century compared to 2011-2020 (Figure 6a). However, by adopting the Delayed Climate Action and Shifting

Pathways scenarios, the increase of impact can be limited to a mean of 100% by the end of the century (Figure 6b, c).

To quantify the beneficial effects to the population brought by different adaptation measures, changes in heat stress impacts are compared against the impacts without adaptation. Each of the adaptation measures in the LMA (Figure 3) lead to a decrease in the total heat stress impact across all climate scenarios in 2061-2070 and 2091-2100 (Figure 7). Among all adaptations, unsealing the urban areas has the most pronounced effect by reducing the mean total population exposed to extreme heat stress days by approximately 37% in 2061-2070 and 27% in 2091-2100. Other adaptations reduce the impacts by less than 5%. Since the impact incorporates the population, unsealing has the biggest impact, as it is located in the most populated areas. The impact calculations only take residing population locations into account. The movements throughout the day and along roads are not considered in the impact analysis. As the locations for tree planting are mainly located in areas with limited population numbers, their impact is substantially smaller in this analysis.

Greatest reductions in heat stress impacts are observed under the alternative climate scenarios. By adopting the Delayed Climate Action scenario, impacts can be reduced by 50 and 73%, whilst the Shifting Pathways scenario achieves reductions of 57% and 76% in 2061 - 2070 and 2091 - 2100 respectively.

Figure 6: The relative change in the sum of the (a - c) population exposed to extreme heat stress days per year, (d - f) population exposed to heatwave days per year, (g - i) average minutes of sleep loss per day in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area under the three scenarios from 2011 to 2100 with reference to the impact in 2011-2020 (the years denoted on the x-axis denote the start of a 10-year period; e.g. 2051 refers to the period 2051-2060). The shaded areas represent the impact derived from the 5th and 95th percentiles of the ensemble of MESMER-M realizations. Please mind the different scale on the y-axis for each row.

Figure 7: The change in the sum of the (a) population exposed to extreme heat stress days per year, (b) population exposed to heatwave days per year, (c) average minutes of sleep loss per day under different adaptations and the climate scenarios relative to no adaptation under Current Climate Policies in 2061-2070 (light) and 2091-2100 (dark). The bars represent the mean value, while the error bars depict the corresponding change in impacts computed from the 5th and 95th percentiles of the ensemble of MESMER-M realizations. Please mind the difference in x-scale between a) b) and c).

The evaluation of the population exposed to heatwave days and the average minutes of sleep loss on the adaptations shows that reducing the carbon emissions by adopting the alternative climate scenarios is the best way to reduce the impact (Figure 7). Adaptations such as unsealing, ecological corridors, and agroforestry in the evaluation of the population exposed

to heatwave days have limited effects and can even worsen the situation by increasing the impact rather than decreasing the impact.

3.2.2. Case studies

The adaptation measures above provided first proof of the potential and limitations of GBI in heat stress adaptation in the LMA at 100 m resolution. In the case studies, we further downscale, by also addressing heat stress at meter-scale (Figure 8).

Vegetation and trees offer efficient lowering of WBGT, similar to the results obtained for the LMA. In general, WBGT values are about 2 °C lower under the shade of a tree compared to areas that are located in direct sunlight. This is observed in all land use and climate scenarios. The reduction in the amount of radiation provides a big relief in heat stress for people traversing the city during the hottest hours of the day. Despite their cooling potential, the case studies show that their cooling is spatially limited to the green areas, which was also experimentally observed by Souverijns et al. (2022) and could also be deduced from the LMA analysis in Figure 5. This advocates for a high abundance of green throughout the whole city, with both street trees and urban parks that provide larger places for cooling, so as many people as possible can benefit from their positive effects. Apart from high vegetation, shade from buildings also lowers heat stress levels, but of a lower magnitude, as these do not provide evaporative cooling and generally have higher land surface temperatures, leading to higher radiation and heat stress levels compared to trees. Low vegetation generally does not generate large decreases in heat stress during heatwave events. This is most pronounced in the Lisbon case study. In the current situation, a high number of open green spaces are present and even though they are covered by low vegetation, they still attain very high levels of heat stress.

This advocates for a good combination of high vegetation and the creation of shady areas in city areas. The Almada case study showcases that this is possible even in historical and highly sealed areas. The trees in the streets provide efficient relief to heat stress and the placing of a park in the currently open space allows for a larger area with substantial cooling for people living in the neighborhood. Similar results are obtained in the E-11 sector in Islamabad. Strategic placing of street trees and larger green areas offers the population multiple options to find relief to the highest heat stress levels. The integration of blue infrastructure helps to continue to provide efficient evaporative cooling.

Current Climate Policies will substantially increase heat stress, temperatures and their impacts, both in Lisbon and Islamabad. The case studies showed that by the end of the

century, even in the shade of trees and with high levels of adaptation, levels of WBGT will be reached that could be potentially dangerous and limit much of the physical activities during several hours of the day. This again showcases that, apart from adaptation, global mitigation options will play an important role to lower heat stress impacts in cities towards the future.

Figure 8: Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT) for present (2020) and future (Current Policies scenario by the end of the century) climate using the original and adaptation land use suggested in Figure 4. Axes denote relative distances in meters from the top left corner.

4. Discussion and conclusion

The use of resilient urban planning via Green and Blue infrastructure (GBI) has been advocated in many studies as a potential tool to adapt to present and climate change induced future heat stress in many regions (Seddon et al., 2020). However, studies quantifying the impacts of their potential benefits are currently largely missing, mainly due to limitations regarding the tools to assess their impacts.

In this study, we presented an integrated methodology to assess the impact of adaptations in urban design on temperatures and heat stress. Using regular stakeholder meetings and the integration of their recommendations, an integrated set of heat adaptation designs have been developed for the Lisbon Metropolitan Area (LMA) and Islamabad. Using the UrbClim, HiREx and CLIMADA models, the effects of these adaptation measures on heat stress and temperatures were calculated, as well as their impacts on the population.

Different adaptation measures showcase different effects on temperature and heat stress. While unsealing was most efficient in reducing nighttime temperatures, greening efforts with high vegetation showcased to be most beneficial for daytime temperatures and heat stress reductions. This distinction has previously been documented both in observational and modelling exercises over different locations of the world (e.g. Ettinger et al. (2024); Gillerot et al. (2024); Eingrüber et al. (2025)). The beneficial effect of high vegetation was also deduced from the detailed case studies we executed, in which the benefits of both individual trees and large tree patches in reducing heat stress was observed. The impact of increasing green infrastructure is however limited to the immediate vicinity of the trees. The importance of choosing the right locations for tree planting is therefore very important, as noted by Hao et al. (2023). This was reflected in the impact studies, where greening had limited effect on the population, as the interventions were mainly limited to areas outside the highly populated areas. Increasing high vegetation could furthermore increase nighttime temperatures, as noted also by Beele et al. (2024). Based on these results, smart urban planning strategies substantiated with scientific evidence need to be designed, to maximize benefits with respect to temperature and heat stress (Wang et al., 2022).

The impact modelling further shows that under a Current Policies scenario, GBI and urban planning alone experience clear adaptation limits. Limits to heat stress adaptation have been raised in the past (e.g. Sherwood & Huber (2010); Seddon et al. (2020)). However, this is one of the first studies to quantify the limits of urban planning at micro-scale level. Although specific adaptation measures can lower impacts on the population, it is noted that mitigation strategies are far more powerful in reducing heat stress and high temperatures. Several studies denote that GBI and urban planning are not enough to countereffect the warming in a Current Policies scenario (e.g. Pascal et al., 2021). These efforts should therefore be combined with other adaptation actions, such as early warning systems (Brimicombi et al., 2024) and strong mitigation efforts to limit the negative impacts of heat stress and high temperatures on the population towards the future (Masselot et al., 2025).

Future research can broaden up by expanding these analyses towards other regions, but also to assess other (co-)benefits of GBI apart from heat stress reductions. In the assessment of

impacts, the movement of the population within the city needs to be considered to improve estimates. Agent-based models are an interesting tool to assess the behavior of citizens during heatwave conditions. Secondly, current and planned vegetation in this study is assumed to provide the same services and benefits towards the future, while in reality adaptation occurs gradually. Furthermore, recent research provides evidence that urban trees might be pushed outside of their safety margin, leading to reduced cooling potential, which should be considered towards the future (Esperon-Rodriguez et al., 2024). Thirdly, variability in vulnerability is not explicitly accounted for in our study, while in reality, vulnerability differs based on age, exposure and adaptive capacity. Lastly, resilient urban planning efficiency modelling could benefit from observation campaigns to both validate the modelling results and provide extra evidence of their impacts on heat stress and temperatures. In conclusion, the UrbClim-HiREx-CLIMADA chain offers a powerful first estimate to quantify heat related (adaptation) impacts and has the potential to provide policy-relevant recommendations to improve heat resilience in cities.

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Data availability

All data can be obtained via https://provide.marvin.vito.be/ftp/adaptation_modelling/

Supplementary Materials

Figure S1: Minimum temperature, maximum temperature, and the number of heat stress days (days with Wet Bulb Globe Temperature exceeding 25°C) for the Lisbon Metropolitan Area averaged over the full period 2011-2020 with present-day land use.

Figure S2: The effect of different adaptation scenarios (rows) on different yearly average climate parameters (columns) in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area under a Current Policies scenario by the end of the century (2091-2100). For temperatures, absolute differences are shown, for heat stress days, the differences are visualized on a relative scale. Thin black lines denote coastlines.

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